

EXPERIMENTAL AND NUMERICAL STUDY ON WEAR PERFORMANCE OF ECO-HYBRID EPOXY COMPOSITE

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the effect of the combinations between Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs) and flax fibre on the adhesive wear performance and mechanical performances of epoxy-based composites. In this study, a 2D modelling of adhesive wear mechanism for Block on ring configuration was simulated based on Archard's wear equation. UMESHMOTION subroutine was coded using FORTRAN and then linked with Abaqus software to describing the adhesive wear test mechanism. The overall effect of temperature and hardness was considered into account by the use of the wear coefficient obtained by experimental tests. The simulation results were verified with the experimental results, and it showed high accuracy in the range of $\pm 13\%$ compared with experiments. The stress field distribution that applied on the wear profile of the samples were analysed.

1 INTRODUCTION

Polymers are increasingly used in many application sectors such as industrial, automotive and in the field of medicine due to their diversity of properties. Polymers have a good ratio of weight to strength, which is highly demanded in industrial, automotive and aerospace applications. In tribological applications, polymers have received much attention because of its lightweight and the distinctive capability of self-lubrication property. This encouraged researchers to improve the wear performance of polymers using fibre reinforcement as well as variant filler materials in order to widen their use. Regarding the effect of solid lubricants nano-fillers, many studies showed a significant impact on the wear performance of polymers. At the same time, it was reported that a significant reduction on the tensile strength as well as the toughness of the basic matrix corresponding with the addition of nano-fillers which promoting fatigue wear mechanism [1, 2]. As reported by Rasheva, Zhang and Burkhart [3], there are no contradictions between the tribological and mechanical characteristics. Therefore, it is desirable to improve the wear performance as well as the mechanical behaviours of polymers. In this context, proposed of the combination of nano-filler and fibre reinforced polymeric composite presents a solution that enhances both behaviours.

From the literature, extensive research studies have been investigated on improving the wear performance of polymers by using synthetic fibres such as glass and carbon fibres. Significant improvements were achieved on both mechanical and tribological behaviours by using these fibres [4].

However, due to the high environmental impact and high-recycling cost of carbon/glass fibre composites, the legislation concerns have motivated research on bio-composites materials [5]. In this context, natural fibres have eco-friendly properties such as renewability and biodegradability, which encouraged the industrial and researchers to explore their performances in such applications.

The current study focuses on the combination effect the GNPs and flax fibre reinforcement on the mechanical and tribological characteristics of epoxy-based composites. The adhesive wear behaviours of epoxy and its composites were performed using block on ring tribometer simulating the real load of bearing applications. Moreover and in order to obtain the mechanical stress and to predicts the worn volume during the rubbing process. The adhesive wear modelling was developed to simulate the adhesive wear process of the block on ring tribometer. The wear model was developed based on Archard's wear equation. UMESHMOTION subroutine was coded using FORTRAN and then linked with the Abaqus model.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

The used materials are described in the first part of this section. The fabrication of two types of epoxy composites is described in the second part. Third part explores the experimental procedures of mechanical and tribological tests. In the last part, the numerical wear model of adhesive wear mechanism is illustrated.

2.1 Material selection

The primary materials used in this investigation are; epoxy resin (R246TX) with the corresponding hardener H160. The epoxy mixture has a density of 1.07 g/cm^3 at 25°C , and HDT of 65°C after 4 hours curing time at 100°C . The epoxy resin was provided by ATL Composites Pty. Ltd., Australia. Epoxy was chosen as the polymer matrix in this study, in which it's the temperature of the curing process suit with natural fibres. Regarding the nano solid lubricant fillers, Graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) of grade C that having $300 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ of average surface area was selected and purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Pty. Regarding the natural fibre reinforcement, unidirectional flax fibre was chosen. A mat of unidirectional flax fibre with an areal density of 200 g/m^2 and a thickness of 0.36 mm was purchased from Lineo, Belgium.

2.2 Composite fabrications

In this study, two different composites were fabricated. In the first stage, the epoxy composites were fabricated based on different weight fraction of GNPs ranging from (0, 1.5 and 3 Wt. %). Neat epoxy was prepared by adding the H160 hardener to the H246RX epoxy resin in a ratio of 1:4 according to supplier instructions. The mixture was string by an electric mixer at a low speed of 250 rpm for two minutes to avoid sudden heat generation. In order to remove created air bubbles, the mixture was kept in the enclosed oven chamber for 30 minutes at 50°C and a constant vacuum pressure of 70 KPa. In case of GNP additions, the GNPs were gradually added to the mixture at the mixing process and then followed by the same procedure of neat epoxy preparation. After that, the mixtures were poured inside specific steel moulds to produce the tensile and wear samples in accordance with ASTM D638-99 and ASTM: G 77 standards, respectively. Curing process passed through the self-curing process at 25°C for 24 hours and then followed by post-curing process inside an oven at 100°C for 4 hours to improve the HDT of all composites.

In the second stage, flax-epoxy composites were fabricated based on different weight fractions of GNPs (0, 1.5 & 3 wt. %) while the volume fraction of flax fibre maintained at $25v_f\%$. Based matrix of neat epoxy and epoxy-GNPs were prepared as described in the first stage. Flax fibre was cutting into required dimensions was the masking tape was used to fixing the fibre during the cutting process. In order to release the trapped humidity inside the flax fibre, the plies were kept on the oven chamber at 60°C for 30 minutes as recommended by the supplier. Flax-epoxy-GNPs composites were prepared

according to the full procedure of vacuum bagging with hand layup technique. Wetted fibre mats were alternately stacked with the base matrix inside the mould. In order to minimise the resin outflow and avoid the signs of starvation fibre, the peel-ply bag was used to envelop the composite during the consolidation stage. Figure 1 illustrates the vacuum layup technique. For tensile samples, six-ply laminates were used with dimensions of 220 mm * 300 mm. For the adhesive wear samples, thirty-ply laminates were used with dimensions of 150 mm * 150 mm. However, the vacuum bagging technique was applied on each six-ply laminates at 95 KPa for ten minutes before gathering all of the thirty laminates, which assist in distributing the matrix inside the fibre mats uniformly. Then the assembly was kept under vacuum pressure of 95KPa and 25°C for 24 hours and then post-cured inside an oven at 100 °C for 4 hours. Finally, the fabricated composites were cut by diamond saw into specific dimensions. For the tensile samples, the thickness was 3 ± 0.2 mm with a length of 250 mm and a width of 25 mm in accordance with ASTM D3039. The adhesive wear samples were cut into the following dimensions (25 mm x 58 mm x 20 mm) in accordance with ASTM G 77 for BOR technique.

Figure 1: Epoxy composites: (a) vacuum bag of the tensile samples; (b) the sectional view of vacuum bag composite.

2.3 Experimental tests

Mechanical characteristics including tensile strength, stiffness and fracture strain were evaluated by tensile test. Toughness values were obtained by integrating the area of engineering stress-strain curves. The tensile test was conducted by MTS 810 TestStar Material testing machine. The crosshead speed was maintained at 1 mm/min in conformity with both standards ASTM D638-99 for epoxy-GNPs composites and ASTM D3039 for flax/epoxy-graphene composite. For repeatability, three samples were tested for each composite material. Shore D hardness values of all different composites were determined by using Durometer-D following ASTM D2240. Three hardness readings were taken for each sample. All data here presents the average reading of three test readings.

Regarding the tribological behaviours, the dry adhesive wear performance of all fabricated composites was performed by using block on ring tribometer. The dimensions of the stainless steel ring and the block (samples) are illustrated in Figure 2- a & b, respectively. A 3D schematic of wear sample and the worn features are illustrated in Figure 2-(c). The tests were conducted at dry contact condition against stainless steel counter-face. The tests were carried out for 6 km of sliding distance and under pressure-velocity (PV) of $0.82 \text{ MPa.m.s}^{-1}$ Where the applied load was 30N and 2 m/s of sliding velocity. These testing parameters were selected to simulate mild adhesive wear for bearing

applications in which the PV value ranging between 0.33 and 3.9 MPa.m.s⁻¹ [6, 7]. The coefficient of friction was obtained by dividing the friction force to the applied load where the friction force was recorded by the Mettler Toledo load cell with 0.0098 N accuracy. The wear coefficient (K) was calculated by two different way based on Archard's wear equation and through microscopic measurements of the geometrical changes by using a surface roughness tester.

Figure 2: Schematic drawings of (a) the AISI 304 stainless steel Ring,(b) the adhesive wear sample of epoxy composites, and (c) 3D schematic illustration of the worn volume.

2.4 Numerical model

In this study, the finite element analysis was implemented to develop a simulation model based on Archard's wear equation (Eq. 1) to compute the worn volume during the sliding. A 2D model was developed to mimic the adhesive wear process at the rubbing zone between the Block (specimen) and ring (counterface). Sliding contact was modelled using adaptive meshing constraint in tow dimensional plane-stress finite element simulation in ABAQUS/Standard. The contact line located between the block (sample) and the ring (stainless steel) renders the problem ideal for 2D modelling, as shown in Fig. 3.

$$\frac{V}{S} = K \frac{F}{H} \quad (1)$$

Where V is the worn volume, S is the sliding distance, K is the wear rate coefficient, F is the normal load and H is the hardness of the material. The wear coefficient was obtained through the applying of Archard's wear equation at the localised contact conditions along with the affected length, which is 20 mm. It worthwhile to mention here that the Archard equation can be localised; hence, it can be easily used by the FE modelling. From the literature, many researchers have used this equation to compute different types of wear for different materials contact pairs such as metal/metal [8, 9] and polymer/metal [10]. Their results have been verified by the experimental test with a good agreement.

The model has consisted of the block of the wear samples in which the contact length is 20 mm, upon which the applied load was equally distributed. The steel counterface was modelled as a rotating ring around its centre similar to the experimental test. As the adhesive wear performance is dependent on the properties of the contacting surfaces rather than the bulk properties [3], it was assumed that the material properties are homogenous for all composites. Experimental values of wear coefficient K and COF were implemented between the two contact bodies. The mesh element was a 4-node bilinear plane stress quadrilateral (CPS4) for both bodies. The mechanical properties of epoxy and its

composites were obtained through the tensile test and tabulated in table.1 (refer to section 3.1). The mechanical properties of AISI 304-stainless ring were obtained from [11].

In order to reduce the computational time of simulation, adaptive wear step was used. Assuming that the K is constant over a specific number of cycles (ΔN). Many attempts were taken to optimise this value. To keep track the surface nodes that subjected to adhesive wear, UMESHMOTION subroutine was used. The UMESHMOTION subroutine was coded by using FORTRAN and then linked with ABAQUS-model. This subroutine that keeps track of the position and material data from the FE model.

Figure 3: Illustration 2D model of BOR contact configuration, showing the FE mesh.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Mechanical and adhesive wear behaviours of epoxy and its composites were performed. The first part of this section explores the mechanical properties and wear performances of epoxy composites. In the second part, the result of wear model is presented, in addition to the verification with the experimental results.

3.1 Experimental results

To simulate the adhesive wear mechanism, the mechanical, frictional, and wear behaviours were determined through the tensile, hardness and the adhesive wear test for all epoxy composites. Table 1 shows the effect of GNPs and the flax fibre on the mechanical properties of epoxy. It can be seen that the incorporation of GNPs has a significant improvement on the stiffness and hardness of epoxy. On another hand, a significant reduction was recorded in fracture strength and its strain as well as the toughness. Improvement on the stiffness could be mainly attributed to the high stiffness value of GNPs which is around 1000 GPa [12]; also the nano-fillers provide a huge surface area per unit mass,

300 m^2/g in this study. However, the primary reason for a high reduction on the fracture strength and its strain as well as toughness is the possibility of aggregations of nano-fillers, which led to low interaction with epoxy matrix and thus playing as a stress raiser. Similar behaviours for nano-fillers /polymers systems were reported, such as graphite/Epoxy [13] and GNPs/PEEK [1].

Regarding the effect of flax fibre. A noticeable enhancement can be seen not only on the stiffness but also on the fracture strength as well as the toughness of the neat epoxy and epoxy-GNP matrix composites. The flax fibre improved the fracture strength and stiffness of neat epoxy about by 116% and 572%, respectively. In the case of the combination between the flax fibre and GNPs fillers, the highest improvement was obtained at the addition of 1.5 wt. % of GNPs, i.e., the fracture strength and stiffness increased by 177%, 614%, respectively. This improvement could be attributed to the increased on the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between the flax fibre and epoxy matrix at this rate of addition. Increasing above this percentage showed less enhancement due to the high possibility of aggregation of nano-fillers inside the matrix. The agglomeration led to low IFSS between the fibre and the matrix and thus reduced the contribution of fibre reinforcement. Similar results have been reported by [14].

	<i>Fracture strength (MPa)</i>	<i>Stiffness (GPa)</i>	<i>Fracture strain, %</i>	<i>Toughness (MJ.m³)</i>	<i>Shore D hardness</i>
Neat Epoxy	61.5±3.3	1.16±0.04	7.9±1.5	2.67±0.71	79.0±0.82
Epoxy-Gr-1.5%	47±3.6	1.26±0.02	4.6±0.33	0.96±0.1	82.3±0.85
Epoxy-Gr-3%	47±2.7	1.32±0.02	4.4±0.42	0.92±0.14	83.3±0.62
Flax/Epoxy	132.0±4.5	7.8±0.6	2.13±0.15	1.52±0.17	81.7±1.25
Flax/Epoxy-Gr-1.5%	130.0±20.5	9.0±0.2	1.62±0.37	1.12±0.37	83.3±0.24
Flax/Epoxy-Gr-3%	108±18.7	7.9±0.4	2.3±0.37	1.5±0.37	85.0±0.41

Table 1: Effects of GNPs and flax fibre on the mechanical properties of epoxy.

Table 2 represents the COF, K and the interface temperature of the epoxy and its composites under the adhesive wear test. GNPs significantly reduced the value of COF confirmed the lubrication capability of graphene. The reduction in COF is due to the transfer film created by the trapped graphene particles that detached from the worn surface. This behaviour is related to the lamellar structure of graphene in which the atoms are coordinated within a hexagonal unit cell inside layers [15]. The bonds between the layers are dominated by the Van der Waals forces, which are easy to fragment by the adhesive shear force [16]. The peeled layers develop into as a thin lubricant layer that effectively reduces the COF. Accordingly, the highest reduction on the K was noticed in case of GNP addition alone. This behaviour could be attributed to the capability of GNPs to produce a stable transfer film [1]. The addition of GNPs reduced the interface temperature of epoxy, which is attributed to their high thermal conductivity which is more than 26,000 times than neat epoxy [17]. However, insignificant reduction on the interface temperature was noticed in case of the flax fibre reinforcement alone.

Flax fibre reinforcement alone exhibits less enhancement on the wear performance of epoxy compared with GNP additions. However, it worthwhile to mention here that the GNPs addition alone significantly reduced the tensile strength and the toughness of epoxy while the flax fibre improved the overall of mechanical properties. Interestingly, it can be seen that the combination of GNPs addition and the flax fibre exhibited a comparable wear performance compared with GNPs addition with high mechanical performance. The addition of GNPs into Flax/epoxy composites exhibits less reduction on the COF, and it might the fibre restrict the generation of the lubricant film compared with Epoxy-GNPs composites.

	<i>COF</i>	<i>K(mm³/N.m 10⁻⁵)</i>	<i>Interface temperature, °C</i>
Neat Epoxy	0.57±0.04	1.04±0.08	49±3
Epoxy-Gr-1.5	0.44±0.35	0.46±0.04	43±3
Epoxy-Gr-3	0.43±0.031	0.31±0.02	41±3
Flax/Epoxy	0.53±0.037	0.66±0.08	46.5±3
Flax/Epoxy-Gr-1.5	0.48±0.036	0.48±0.07	43.4±3
Flax/Epoxy-Gr-3	0.46±0.036	0.42±0.06	42.5±3

Table 2: Effect of GNPs and the flax fibre on the wear performance of epoxy.

Figure 4 shows the SEM micrograph of the worn surface of epoxy and its composites after adhesive wear testing. The worn surface of neat epoxy (Fig. 4-a) exhibits signs of fragmentation and softening. However, in case of GNP additions, the worn surface of the samples was paved with a transfer film, which explains the reduction on the COF and *K* of epoxy-GNPs composites. In case of the combination of flax fibre and GNPs additions, the worn surfaces have a smooth surface and unclear transfer film.

Figure 4: SEM Micrographs of epoxy composites after adhesive wear test: (a) Neat epoxy, (b) epoxy-GNPs-1.5, (c) epoxy-GNPs-3, (d) flax/epoxy, (e) flax/epoxy-GNPs-1.5 and (f) flax/epoxy-GNPs-3.

3.2 SIMULATION RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the dependence of contact pressure as well as the contact area of the neat epoxy sample on the sliding distance. It can be seen that the contact area increases with increasing sliding distance and then the applied force distributed over a larger contact area, which led to reduce the contact pressure. Figure 6 displays the distribution of von Mises stress in the wear profiles at mid and the end of a sliding distance of 6 km. Similarly, figure 7 shows the counters of shear stress. The sliding direction was from the right to left, as indicated by the arrows. Clearly, the counters show that the direction of sliding has an important effect on stress distribution. The maximum stresses were noticed for all cases at the starting point of the rubbing process. Despite the reduction on the contact pressure with the sliding distance as shown in figure 5, an insignificant increase was noticed on the stress values at 6 km of sliding distance compared with 3 km. It seems that the slope of the wear curve plays an important role in distributing the stress leading to like this phenomenon.

Figure 5: Change of contact pressure (solid line) and contact area (dashed line) during the progressive of wear process.

Figure 8 shows the wear profiles of the epoxy composite samples after 6 km of sliding distance. The maximum wear depth was corresponding with neat epoxy, and it was 29.66 μm localized at the centre of sample width. In order to verify the wear model results, the maximum wear depth was determined experimentally by using the surface roughness tester. There as a good agreement between the experimental and the result of the wear model, as shown in figure 9-a. Figure 9-b shows the volume loss versus the sliding distance of neat epoxy for both cases experimental and through the wear simulation. The wear results are in a high agreement matching with the experimental results.

Figure 6: FE generated contours of von Mises stress (50 times scaled up) at the contact zone at (a) after 3 km of sliding distance and (b) after 6 km of sliding distance.

Figure 7: FE generated contours of shear stress (50 times scaled up) at the contact zone at (a) after 3 km of sliding distance and (b) after 6 km of sliding distance.

The simulation prediction was in closer agreement with the experimental data in the longer sliding distance. This could be related to the high rate of change of the wear coefficient K at the beginning of the rubbing process. From the literature, the general trend of K starts with relatively high value with a gradual decrease along the sliding distance, and it becomes stable in the steady-state region. This phenomenon is known as the running-in process, in which the asperities are at the interaction process leading to high material removal from the soft rubbed surface [18], which here epoxy and its composites. From figure 9-b, the wear volume obtained from the Simulation is with a percentage error of 11% compared with experimental results while it is around 29 % just at the first one kilometre of sliding distance. However, the overall error is 13%, which is within the standard deviation of the experimental investigation.

Figure 8: The wear profiles of the epoxy and its composites by UMESHMOTION subroutine-simulation.

Figure 9: Comparison wear volume of neat epoxy between experimental and numerical results for neat epoxy: (a) the wear profile of simulation with the wear depth of experimental after adhesive wear test and (b) the wear volume vs sliding distance.

4. Conclusions

The epoxy composites based on the flax fibre and different weight fractions of Graphene Nanoplatelets (GNPs) were fabricated. The mechanical properties were determined, and the dry adhesive wear behaviours of all fabricated composites were performed using the block on ring tribometer. While GNPs additions were offering the best wear behaviour, they cause a significant reduction in the strength and toughness of the epoxy matrix. However, the combination of flax fibre and GNPs exhibited a comparable performance to the wear performance of epoxy-GNP composites with having high mechanical properties.

In the second part of this study, a 2D numerical model was developed to simulate the adhesive wear process for the block on ring configuration. This model was used to determine the wear loss during the rubbing process, in addition to understanding the effect of the geometrical changes on the contact stress of the worn area of the wear sample. The simulation results showed an agreement with the experimental results in the prediction of wear volume in the steady-state region. Moreover, the numerical model is offering a better understanding of the wear mechanism as a function of the geometrical change in the contact surfaces due to progressive wear. In the case of the BOR configuration system, the increase in the wear depth led to increasing of the mechanical stress at the starting point of the sliding process while the contact pressure showed a high reduction.

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